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PREVALENCE OF HEPATITIS C VIRUS (HCV) AND MEASLES VIRUS (MeV) INFECTION AMONG CHILDREN OF THE SOUTH-EAST REGION OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Measles virus (MeV) and Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) belongs to different viral families. Their major difference is that MeV is a vaccine preventable childhood infectious agent while HCV is a persistent infection, without vaccine. Children may contract HCV while in uterus but MeV spreads within a community via air inhalation and contacts. Thus, this study was aimed at determining the prevalence and risk factors of co-infection of measles virus (MeV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV) in children in the South-East region of Nigeria. This was a cross-sectional study design, with the enrolled children drawn from the South East region of Nigeria. A

structured questionnaire was used to obtain information about the children from their parents or guardian. Blood samples were collected and serum extracted, and stored in cryovials at -170°C until tested. The sera samples were screened for anti-HCV antibodies and anti-measles IgM antibodies using their separate ELISA kits. The data were subjected to statistically analysis and significant level taken at $p \leq 0.05$. A total of 180 children were recruited for the study. They included 47.2% males and 52.8% females respectively, with mean age of 3.9 ± 2.4 years old. Prevalence rate of 71.7%, 8.9% and 8.3% were obtained for MeV, HCV and MeV/HCV respectively, while 0.6% was sero-positive for HCV-antibodies only. Within the region, Abia State recorded the highest prevalence of MeV and HCV at rate of 21.6% and 3.3% respectively. The age group of 4.0 -5.9 were mostly affected with a prevalence rate of 3.3% and 19.4% for HCV and MeV. The co-infection was 2.2% for both viruses. The occurrence of eye discharges and rash/postules were significantly significant for measles virus infection. The predictor for measles virus infection was eye discharge. The co-infection of MeV and HCV at a prevalence rate of 8.3% within the region, remains a significant public health concern for the children, as HCV may complicate the course of measles infection, increasing morbidity and healthcare burden.

KEYWORDS: MeV (Measles virus), HCV (Hepatitis C Virus), HCV/MeV co-infection, South-East Region of Nigeria, Children, seroprevalence.

INTRODUCTION

Viral co-infections in children remain an important but under-recognized public health challenge, particularly in regions with high endemicity of multiple pathogens. Among these, hepatitis C virus (HCV) –a blood-borne hepatotropic virus capable of causing chronic liver disease, and measles- a highly contagious viral infection known for its immunosuppressive effects (Krawiec & Hinson, 2023), represent two distinct but clinically significant infections. Co-infection with other viruses modifies the viral profile in serum and leads to more liver damage and more rapid progression during the course of the viral infection (Lin *et al.*, 2006). Viral co-infections identified from pediatric measles cases may contribute to increased disease severity and high rate of fatal outcome (Hang *et al.*, 2017).

Children represent only a small proportion of those infected with the hepatitis (HCV) compared to adults. Nevertheless, a substantial number of children have chronic HCV infection and are at risk of complications including cirrhosis, portal hypertension, with hepatic encephalopathy and carcinoma in adulthood (Jarasvaraparn *et al.*, 2024). Globally, the prevalence of HCV infection in children was approximately 0.87% (Melikoki *et al.*, 2021). In the United States, the prevalence of HCV among children was estimated at approximately 0.2% (aged 1-11 years) to 0.4% (aged 12-19 years) (Alter *et al.*, 1999) and later fell to less than 0.1% in the subsequent decades (Denniston *et al.*, 2014). However, higher rates are reported in developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa and part of Asia where unsafe medical practices and vertical transmission contribute significantly to pediatric HCV infection (Walsey & Alter, 2000). The estimated prevalence of HCV in African children was approximately 3.02% (Melikoki *et al.*, 2021). A community-based study in Ibadan, Nigeria reported an HCV antibody seroprevalence of about 2.0% in children (Okonko *et al.*, 2012). In the upper west region of Ghana, the seroprevalence of HCV in children has been reported to be 2.9% (Avege, 2016).

Hepatitis C is a viral disease that leads to swelling (inflammation) of the liver. Hepatitis C infection is caused by hepatitis C virus. Hepatitis C virus (HCV) is a hepatotropic virus. Infection with hepatitis C virus has been identified as the major cause of post-transfusion non-A, non-B hepatitis'' (Yeung *et al.*, 2022). Mohamed *et al.*, (2015) reported that Hepatitis C virus is a well-known agent of liver diseases including chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma while

Michielsen *et al.*, (2005) posited that Hepatitis C virus is an enveloped virus, with a positive sense single-stranded RNA genome, approximately 10kb in length, with similarity in genome organization and some sequence homology with pestiviruses and flaviviruses

Hepatitis C virus strains are classified into six genotypes (1-7) each comprising of multiple subtypes designated (a, b, c) as indicated by Simmonds *et al.*, (2005). A seventh genotype (subtype 7a) was subsequently reported by Murphy *et al.*, (2015). Many of these HCV types comprises of a number of more closely related subtypes, leading to a current total of 11 genetically distinct viral populations (Simmonds *et al.*, 2005). Razavi *et al.*, (2013) further reported that HCV genome has a high degree of genetic heterogeneity due to the error-prone nature of its RNA-dependent RNA polymerase, resulting in extensive sequences diversity based on the reported of Li & Lemon, (2012).

Measles, on the other hand, remains a leading cause of vaccine-preventable morbidity and mortality in children, especially in low-income and middle-income countries where vaccination coverage is suboptimal (WHO, 2023). Beyond its characteristics rash and respiratory symptoms, measles induces profound but transient immunosuppression, predisposing children to secondary infections and prolonged viral persistence (Mina *et al.*, 2015).

Measles is highly contagious, serious airborne disease, vaccine preventable disease caused by measles virus that can lead to severe complications and death (WHO, 2024). It is an acute viral infection that can lead to severe morbidity and mortality in children (Paules *et al.*, 2019). Despite the availability of effective vaccines, measles continues to be a significant cause of illness and mortality globally, resulting in approximately 100,000 deaths annually (Paules *et al.*, 2019). In 2011, the Global Measles and Rubella Strategic Plan was established by the World Health Organization aimed to achieve measles elimination by the end of 2020. Measles also called rubeola, morbilli, ‘10- day measles, or red measles’, can affect anyone but it is most common in children. It is an airborne disease which can spread easily from one person to another through cough and sneezing. Measles targets the respiratory tracts and then spread throughout the body (WHO, 2024). Patients with a history of typical measles have extremely high level of measles antibodies.

The mechanism of measles is obscure, symptoms usually begin 10-14 days after exposure to the virus. A prominent rash is the most visible symptom, others are fever, dry cough, runny nose, sore throat and inflamed eyes (conjunctivitis) (Misin *et al.*, 2020). Measles remains a critical public health threat in Nigeria, with high incidence rates and low vaccination coverage (Olufadewa *et al.*, 2024). The overall pooled prevalence of measles-confirmed cases was 67.6% (Eshetu *et al.*, 2024). In Nigeria, challenges with the healthcare system, such as lack of resources and facilities, can exacerbate the severity and transmission of measles. One of the most unique- and most dangerous –feature of measles pathogenesis is its ability to reset the immune systems of infected patients (Hagen, 2019).

Measles hepatitis is more common in children than adults, the damage is generally hepatocellular and it is caused by direct viral action (Mohiuddin *et al.*, 2017). The co-infection of hepatitis C virus (HCV) and measles (MeV) is rare and not well documented. A study by Andjaparidze *et al.*, (1989) identified measles virus genome fragments in lymphocytes of patients with autoimmune chronic active hepatitis, suggesting possible persistent MeV presence in chronic inflammatory liver conditions.

A Nigerian study documented co-infection of viral hepatitis and other viral diseases among children, underscoring the potential for overlapping infections in endemic areas. Lawal *et al.*,

(2020) reported on hepatitis B and C viral co-infection in HIV infected children in Lagos, Nigeria. Similarly, Eze *et al.*, (2014), reported a prevalence rate of 6.8% HCV and HIV co-infection among children in Enugu, Nigeria. In Tanzania, a study reported an HCV seroprevalence of 13.8% among HIV-infected children (Telatela *et al.*, 2007). However, there has been no reported data on the prevalence of HCV and measles co-infection in pediatric populations in the South East region, and global data remain extremely scarce, highlighting a significant gap in current epidemiological knowledge.

Hence, this study is aimed at determining the prevalence of Hepatitis C Virus (HCV), measles (MeV) infection and HCV/ MeV co-infection among children of the South East region of Nigeria, using patients attending general hospitals across the five South-East states.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- **Study Design**

The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional design to determine the prevalence of measles virus infection, hepatitis C virus infection and their co-infection among children suspected of contracting measles.

- **Study Area**

The study was conducted during a surveillance study on measles in the South-East region of Nigeria. The subjects were recruited from various health care facilities where children with suspected measles are routinely evaluated, across Enugu, Ebonyi, Abia, Anambra and Imo states.

- **Study Population**

The targeted population consist of children aged 0-15 years who present with measles-like symptoms, and are referred to laboratory testing. A total of 150 samples were obtained for the study.

- **Ethical Consideration**

The Health Research Ethics Committee of Enugu State Ministry of Health reviewed and approved the study protocol. The study participants voluntarily completed an informed assent form while confidentiality was maintained using coded identifiers.

- **Sample Size Determination**

The sample size for the study was determined using the equation described by Naing *et al.*, (2006).

$$n = \frac{Z^2 * P [1 - P]}{E^2} \quad \text{equation (1)}$$

Where;

n = Minimum sample size required

Z = Z-score corresponding to 95% confidence level (1.96)

P = Prevalence of HCV among apparently healthy children in Ibadan in Oyo state by Okonko *et al.*, (2015)

E = Margin of error tolerated (0.05)

Hence

$$n = \frac{([1.96]^2 \times 0.09 [1 - 0.09])}{[0.05]^2} \quad \text{equation (2)}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.09 \times 0.91}{0.0025} \quad \text{equation (3)}$$

$$n = 126$$

Hence, the minimum sample size was 126 subjects.

An attrition rate of 20% was anticipated,

$$= 20\% \text{ of } 126$$

$$= \frac{20 \times 126}{100}$$

$$= 25.2$$

$$= 25.2 + n$$

$$= 25.2 + 126 = 151$$

- **Inclusion and exclusion Criteria**

Children (aged 0-15 years) clinically suspected of having measles, children whose parents or guardians provided informed assent, and children whose blood samples are successfully collected were included for the study. Children previously confirmed to have measles before presentation and children whose parents or guardians decline consent were excluded.

- **Clinical Assessment of Subject**

Children with symptoms suggesting measles (fever, rash, coughs, coryza, conjunctivitis, swollen lymph nodes) were evaluated. Demographic and clinical information was collected using a structured questionnaire.

- **Collection of Samples**

Blood samples were collected under aseptic conditions from the participants in a plain tubes and serum extracted. The serum was stored at cryovial and kept at -80°C until tested.

- **Analysis of Samples**

Hepatitis C virus antibody test.

The anti-HCV kit employs solid phase, indirect ELISA method for detection of antibodies to HCV in two-step incubation procedure. Polystyrene micro-well strips are pre-coated with recombinant, highly immune-reactive antigens corresponding to the core and the non-structural regions of HCV (fourth generation HCV ELISA).

During the first incubation step, anti-HCV specific antibodies if present, will be bound to the solid phase pre-coated HCV antigens. The wells are washed to remove unbound serum proteins, and

rabbit anti-human IgG antibodies (anti-IgG) conjugated to horseradish peroxidase (HRP-Conjugate) is added.

During the second incubation step, these HRP-Conjugated antibodies will be bound to any antigen-antibody (IgG) complexes previously formed and the unbound HRP-Conjugate is then removed by washing.

Chromogen solutions containing Tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) and urea peroxidase are added to the wells and in presence of the antigen-antibody-anti-IgG (HRP) immune-complex; the colorless chromogens are hydrolyzed by the bound HRP conjugate to a blue-color product. The blue color turns yellow after stopping the reaction with sulphuric acid. The amount of color intensity can be measured and is proportional to the amount of antibody captured in the wells, and to the sample respectively. Wells containing samples negative for anti-HCV remain colorless.

Detection of Measles IgM

Presence of IgM antibodies indicates active or current measles infection. One hundred microliter (100ul) of patient's serum was added into wells coated with anti-human IgM antibodies. Controls (positive and negative), and calibrators were added, incubated at 37⁰ C for 30-60 minutes. The well was washed to remove unbound materials. Conjugates labelled with anti-human IgM antibodies was added to each well, incubated at 37⁰ C for 30-60 minutes. It was washed again to remove unbound conjugate. Tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) substrate was added to the wells, incubated in the dark for 10 -20 minutes at room temperature. Stop solution (phosphoric acid) was added to each well. The enzyme reacts with the substrate produces blue colour which later turns yellow with stop solution. Absorbance was read at 450 nm using ELISA reader. Colour change indicated presence of measles IgM (recent infection- positive), no colour change indicated negative test.

- **Statistical analysis**

All data were entered and statistically analyzed using the IBM Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 29, which determines the presence and strength of the association between the dependent and independent variables, and p-values <0.05 (level of significant) was considered as a cut point.

RESULTS

A total of 180 children had their serum analyzed. The children were recruited from the South East geographical regions of Nigeria. The children were recruited from Enugu state, Abia state, Anambra state, Imo state and Ebonyi state at a frequency of 28.3%, 24.4%, 20.6%, 15.6% and 11.1% respectively as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Sample Collection from South East Region

States	F	Percent (%)
Abia State	44	24.4
Anambra State	37	20.6
Enugu State	51	28.3
Ebonyi State	20	11.1
Imo State	28	15.6
Total	180	100

- **Demographic Characteristics of the Children**

The subjects comprise of 47.2% (85/180) males and 52.8% (95/180) females. With mean age of 3.9 ± 2.4 years old, with a range of 0.75 – 11.0 years old. Majority of the subjects were of the age group of 2.1 -3.9 years old constituting 27.8 % (50/180) while those of 6.0 -11.0 were 17.3% (32/180). Most of the children along with their parents were from the rural areas with a frequency of 39.4% (71/180) while those of the urban and semi-urban areas were 30.6% (55/180) and 30.0% (54/180) respectively (Table 2).

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of the subjects:

Variables	f	Percent (%)
Sex		
Male	85	47.2
Female	95	52.8
Ages (years)		
≤2	49	27.2
2.1 – 3.9	50	27.8
4.0 – 4.9	49	27.2
6.0 – 11.0	32	17.3
Residence		
Rural	71	39.4
Semi-urban	54	30.0
Urban	55	30.6

- **Seroprevalence of Measles and HCV Infection**

Out of the 180 children enrolled in this study, 71.7% (129/180) and 8.9% (16/180) were seropositive for measles IgM and anti- HCV antibodies respectively. Co-infection of HCV and measles IgM was detected in 8.3% (15/180) of the children while 0.6% (1/180) was detected in a child without measles as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of the sero-positive measles and HCV antibodies

Parameter	Positive (f)	Percent (%)
Anti HCV antibodies	16	8.9
Measles IgM	129	71.7
Anti- HCV-Ab / measles IgM	15	8.3
Anti-HCV-Abs only	1	0.6

- **Regional Distribution**

The distribution of measles and HCV among the states in South-East region indicated that Abia state ranked highest with 21.6% (39/180), 3.3% (6/180), 3.3% (6/180) of measles, HCV and measles/ HCV infections respectively. In Enugu, Ebonyi, Imo and Anambra states, the seroprevalence of measles were as follows: 18.3% (33/180), 8.9% (16/180), 12.8% (23/180) and 10.0% (18/180) respectively. The sero-prevalence of HCV in Enugu, Ebonyi, Imo and Anambra states were 1.1% (2/180), 2.2% (4/180), 1.7% (3/180) and 0.6% (1/180), while in Anambra the co-

infection was not obtained but was detected at a prevalence rate of 2.2% (4/180), 1.1% (2/180) and 1.7% (3/180) in Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo states. The occurrence of measles and co-infection of HCV/measles were statistically significant in the South-East region, $p = 0.001$ and $p = 0.020$ respectively (Table 4).

Table 4: Sero-positivity of HCV and Measles antibodies in relation to South- east region

Variables	f (%)	f (%)	f (%)
States of origin	HCV +ive	(MeV) +ive	HCV/MeV +ive
Abia State	6 (3.3)	39 (21.6)	6 (3.3)
Anambra State	1 (0.6)	18 (10.0)	0 (0.0)
Enugu State	2 (1.1)	33 (18.3)	2 (1.1)
Ebonyi State	4 (2.2)	16 (8.9)	4 (2.2)
Imo State	3 (1.7)	23 (12.8)	3 (1.7)
Total	16 (8.9)	129 (71.7)	15 (8.3)
p-value	0.084	0.001*	0.020*

Key: * (is used to indicate p-values that are statistically significant, that is ≥ 0.05)

- **Demographic Characteristics**

The sero-prevalence of HCV was more in females than males with 7.2% (13/180) and 1.7% (3/180) respectively and it was statistically significant, $p = 0.017$. The measles infection though not statistically significant was obtained in 36.1 % (65/180) of the females and 35.5% (64/180) of males. It was observed that co-infection of measles and HCV were more in females than males, this was statistically significant, $p = 0.006$. The age distribution of the children showed not statistically significant but those ≥ 3 years had the highest measles infection with 1.7%. The age groups 4.0 -5.9, 2.0 – 3.9 and 6.0 – 11.0 had 19.4%, 18.3%, and 12.8% of measles respectively. The anti-HCV antibodies obtained rate of 2.2%, 1.7%, 3.3%, and 2.2% among the age's groups of 2.0 - 3.9, 4.0 – 5.9 and 6.0 – 11.0 respectively (Table 5).

Table 5: Demographic Characteristics of the Children

Variables	HCV+ve	Measles IgM +ve	HCV/Measles +ve
Sex:			
Male	3 (1.7)	64 (35.5)	2 (1.1)
Female	13 (7.2)	65 (36.1)	13 (7.2)
p-value	0.017*	0.307	0.006*
Age (years)			
≤ 2	4 (2.2)	38 (21.1)	4 (2.2)
2.0 – 3.9	3 (1.7)	33 (18.3)	3 (1.7)
4.0—5.9	6 (3.3)	35 (19.4)	4 (2.2)
6.0—11.0	4 (2.2)	23 (12.3)	4 (2.2)
p-value	0.722	0.658	0.786
Residence:			
Rural	7 (3.9)	54 (30.0)	7 (3.9)
Semi-urban	5 (2.9)	35 (19.4)	5 (2.8)
Urban	4 (2.2)	40 (22.2)	3 (1.7)
p-value	0.313	0.377	0.663

- **Assessment of the Risk Factors**

The children that received measles vaccination recorded 56.7% (102/180) positive for measles IgM and 7.8% (14/180) HCV positivity while co-infection of measles and HCV accounted for 7.2% (13/180) positivity. Among unvaccinated individuals, 15% (27/180) were seropositive for measles IgM antibodies, compared to 1.1% (2/180) HCV antibodies, with a co-infection rate of 1.1% (2/180) observed. The measles vaccination was not statistically significant on the outcome of both the measles and HCV infection.

The presence of eye pus discharge was significantly associated with measles positivity ($p < 0.001$). Among participants with eye discharge, 56.7% (102/ 180) were positive for measles IgM antibodies, compared to only 0.6% (1/ 180) among those without eye discharge. The children with skin rashes/ postule and measles IgM positivity were 58.9% (106/180) as against 12.8% (23/180) that had measles IgM positivity but without skin rashes. This was statistically significant ($p = 0.013$). The children with HCV/ measles positivity and skin rashes were also statistically significant ($p = 0.024$). There are other factors that were not statistically significant which include; blood transfusion, fever and febrile seizure (Table 6).

Table 6: Assessment of the Risk Factors

Variables	HCV +ve	Measles +ve	HCV/ Measles +ve
Previous measles vaccination			
Yes	14 (7.8)	102 (56.7)	13 (7.2)
No	2 (1.1)	27 (15.0)	2 (1.1)
p-value	0.743	0.620	0.739
Koplit spot			
Yes	6 (3.3)	48 (26.7)	0 (0.0)
No	10 (5.6)	81 (45.0)	0 (0.0)
p-value	0.831	0.224	0.582
Vomiting			
Yes	13 (7.2)	98 (54.4)	12 (6.7)
No	3 (1.7)	31 (17.2)	3 (1.7)
p-value	0.562	0.074	0.764
Eye discharges			
Yes	15 (8.3)	102 (56.7)	14 (7.8)
No	1 (0.6)	27 (15.0)	1 (0.6)
p-value	0.473	<0.001*	0.703
Diarrhea			
Yes	14 (7.8)	102 (56.7)	13 (7.2)
No	2 (1.1)	27 (15.0)	2 (1.1)
p-value	0.367	0.225	0.526
Febrile seizure			
Yes	1 (0.6)	4 (2.2)	1 (0.6)
No	15 (8.3)	125 (69.4)	14 (7.8)
p-value	1.000	1.000	0.411
History of blood transfusion			
Yes	1 (0.6)	12 (6.7)	1 (0.6)
No	15 (8.3)	117 (65.0)	14 (7.8)
p-value	1.000	0.620	1.000
Fever			
Yes	8 (4.4)	77 (42.8)	8 (4.4)
No	8 (4.4)	52 (28.9)	7 (3.6)
p-value	0.509	0.409	0.716
Skin rash /Postule			
Yes	15 (8.3)	106 (58.9)	15 (8.3)
No	1 (0.6)	23 (12.8)	0 (0.0)
p-value	0.125	0.012*	0.024*

- **Logistics Regression Analysis**

The occurrence of HCV antibody and measles IgM co-infections among the children within the South East region were compared across the study states. Children from Abia, Ebonyi and Imo States were found to be 3.90, 6.12 and 2.94 times more likely, respectively, to acquire HCV/measles co-infection compared to those from Enugu state (reference group). The 95% confidence intervals (CI) for these odds ratios (OR) were 0.73 – 20.25 for Abia, 1.02- 36.64 for Ebonyi and 0.46 – 19.75 for Imo State. Of importance, the gender differences revealed that the male children were 6.58 times more likely to acquire HCV/measles co-infection more than the female children. The 95% confidence interval (CI) for this association was 1.44 – 30.07 ($p = 0.006$).

Analysis across the South East region showed that children from Abia, Enugu, Ebonyi and Imo States showed a significant higher risk of acquiring measles virus infection compared to those from Anambra State (reference group) ($p = 0.001$). Moreover, analysis revealed that female subjects were 4.33 times more likely to acquire HCV infection compared to male subjects (reference group). The 95% confidence interval for this association was 1.19- 15.78. (0.017).

Children with measles infection were 7.27 times more likely to develop eye pus discharge than those that were not infected with measles (95% CI: 2.99 – 17.67). When odd ratio (OR) was adjusted, there was no major difference in outcome (95% CI: 7.22 (2.80 – 18.61)). The presence of skin rash/postule showed that each individual were 2.51 times of suffering measles complication (Table 7).

Table 7: Logistic Regression Analysis

Variables	p-value	OR (95% CI)	p-value	AOR (95%CI)
HCV:				
Sex	0.017			
Male (Ref)				
Female		4.33 (1.19- 15.78)		
Measles:				
South East region	0.001*			
Abia		8.23 (2.65 - 25.54)		
Enugu		1.94 (0.82 – 4.59)		
Ebonyi		4.22 (1.18 – 15.05)		
Imo		4.87 (1.52 - 15.52)		
Anambra (Ref)				
HCV/ measles-				
Sex:	0.006*			
Male		6.58 (1.44- 30.07)		
Female				
HCV/ measles:				
South East region:	0.020*			
Abia		3.90 (0.73 – 20.25)		
Ebonyi		6.12 (1.02 – 36.64)		
Imo		2.94 (0.46 – 19.75)		
Enugu (Ref)				

Eye discharge (measles):	<0.001*		<0.001*	
Yes		7.27 (2.99 – 17.67)		7.22 (2.80-18.61)
No (Ref)				
Skin rash/ postule (measles)	0.012*	2.51 (1.21 – 6.21)	0.010*	3.02 (1.30- 7.02)

The bivariate analysis of HCV and measles sero-positivity revealed a co-infection prevalence of 8.3%, while 0.6% of the subjects had HCV infection without measles. This association was statistically significant with p-value of 0.043 and odd ratio (OR) of 6.58 (95% CI: 0.85 – 51.17) Table 7.

Table 7: Bivariate analysis of HCV and measles positivity

	Positive (f)	Negative (f)	p-value	OR (95%CI)
Positive	15	1	0.043	6.57 (0.85 – 51.17)
Negative	114	50		Ref

DISCUSSION

The seroprevalence of anti-measles IgM obtained was 71.7% while that of anti-HCV antibody recorded 8.9%. The co-infection of HCV and measles virus was observed in 8.3% of the children whereas only 0.6% of the children had only HCV infection. In a similar study, Duedu *et al.* (2021) reported a lower prevalence of 0.5% of HCV infection in children in Ghana. Okonko *et al.* (2015) reported a prevalence rate of 0.9% of HCV infection among apparently healthy children in Ibadan, Oyo State. This study involved states in the South East Nigeria which is a combination of 5 states. The combined HCV prevalence rate of 8.9% may be due to HCV carrier status of their respective mothers. Benova *et al.* (2014) showed that 6-11% of children born to HCV mothers acquires it through vertical transmission.

A high prevalence of 71.7% measles IgM is of public health importance because either that there is a vaccine failure due to poor sero-conversion of the vaccines administered to children or that the children were not vaccinated due to non-coverage of the rural areas. A lower prevalence of 44.4% of measles IgM was obtained in Sokoto State by Iduh *et al.* (2024). Adekola *et al.* (2021) reported 14.6% measles IgM among children with symptoms of measles in Abuja. Similarly, Olaitan *et al.* (2015) reported 21.2 % of measles IgM in children with measles-like symptoms in Kaduna State. The high prevalence of measles IgM in this study is a reflection of poor measles vaccination program. Measles virus is a childhood preventable disease with vaccine while hepatitis C virus remains a viral disease with primary infection site in the liver and its impact increases with age. In this study, the co-infection of HCV and measles IgM was observed in 8.3% of the children. This finding indicated that a subset of such population has concurrent or recent exposure of both viruses.

Although measles and HCV are caused by unrelated pathogens, their co-existence in children has clinical and epidemiological significance. Papadopoulou *et al.* (2001) reported that 4.8% of children had hepatitis (inflammation of the liver). The occurrence of HCV and measles co-infection may reflect the immunological and environmental factors that favour viral coexistence. Measles infection is known to induce transient immunosuppression, predisposing the affected individuals to secondary bacterial or viral infections (Mina *et al.* 2015). Conversely, chronic HCV infections, which leads to persistent liver inflammation, may impair immune responses and

complicate recovery from acute infections such as measles (Alter & Seeff, 2000). This interaction could contribute to greater hepatic involvement and prolonged illness, as both viruses are capable of influencing liver enzyme levels and systemic immune function (Cohen *et al.* 2017). The observed co-infection rate, though relatively low, is epidemically relevant, particularly in regions where both measles and HCV remain endemic. The presence of dual infections may also reflect shared transmission risks, such as unsafe medical procedures, poor sanitation, or limited access to vaccination and healthcare services (WHO, 2023).

The spread of measles and HCV was evident in the 5 states of the south-east region. The presence of measles IgM and measles/HCV co-infection were statistically significant within these regions. Abia state has the highest HCV, measles and HCV/measles co-infection. This indicates that south-east region had concurrent measles and HCV co-infection among children.

The demographic characteristics of the subjects indicated that the male-female gender was statistically significant for HCV and HCV/measles co-infection. The females with 7.2 % of HCV positive were all positive for HCV/ measles. Implication of this is that these female subjects may grow with HCV infection to become carriers of HCV. The age specificity of the subjects shows that 4.0-5.9 years old recorded 3.3%, 19.4% and 2.2% of HCV, measles, and HCV/measles co-infections respectively. This represent nursery school children, indicating that measles virus may have been contracted from the school environment due to playing together. Although the age of the children was not statistically significant, there may be spread of HCV/ measles co-infection among age group, and the infection may grow with them to act as sources of transmission to others. Galoppo and Galoppo (2010) reported that age-dependent increase occurs due to cumulative exposures to infection risk factors.

The risk factors accessed in this study indicated that eye discharge was statistically significant for measles IgM. Children with measles often present with red, watery, photophobia and thick discharges, which may affect eyelids to stick together, especially in the morning. American Academy of Ophthalmology (2025), reported that if eye discharge is not managed appropriately in measles, the inflammation may progress to corneal ulceration, keratitis and even permanent visual impairment. It is also known that measles infection can induce skin rash/postules (also called maculopapular rash). In this study, measles and HCV/measles co-infection were statistically significant for skin rash/postules. According to Griffin (2021), the hallmark of maculopapular rash of measles appears within 10-14 days after infection.

CONCLUSION

The coexistence of HCV and measles suggests potential immunological interaction, where measles-induced immunosuppression may enhance vulnerability to other infections, chronic HCV may worsen the hepatic effects of measles. These findings emphasize the need for integrated disease control strategies, including strengthening routine measles immunization, promoting safe injection and blood transfusion practices, and implementing HCV screening among children presenting with measles-associated hepatitis (Lanini *et al.* 2016). Furthermore, this result highlights the need for gender-sensitive public health strategies in the prevention and control of both HCV and measles infections in pediatric populations. Early detection and management of such cases can prevent complications and reduce diseases burden. Public health programs should therefore consider combining immunization campaigns with viral hepatitis awareness and testing initiatives, especially during measles outbreaks (Khetsuriani *et al.* 2019).

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